

Personality Traits as Determinants of Burnout among Nurses – A Correlational Study**Author's Details:**

⁽¹⁾**Zainab Hamid**-Research Scholar, Department Of Psychology, University Of Kashmir

⁽²⁾**Dr.Shawkat Ahmad Shah**-Associate Professor, Department Of Psychology, University Of Kashmir

Abstract

Background: The conditions of uncertainty and disempowerment at hospitals with high organizational demands threaten both physical and emotional wellbeing of nurses which in turn may contribute to burnout and disengagement or withdrawal of nurses from their organizations. At the same time their role in delivering the services to the society has prompted the experts to discuss, debate, and examine the multitude of practices to make them more productive.

Objectives: The present study was carried out with the main objective of understanding the relation of personality traits with burnout among nurses and to identify significant personality traits that determine burnout among them.

Design and methods: A quantitative and correlational research design was adopted and the settings included hospitals/nursing homes of J&K, India. The participants included the 300 nurses having at least two years of working experience and selected/engaged by the authorities on substantive basis. Standardised tools were used to collect the data, Pearson's product moment correlation method and regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses.

Results: Results revealed that openness to experience ($r = -0.126$, P value 0.05); conscientiousness ($r = -0.317$, P value 0.01); extraversion ($r = -0.246$, P value 0.01); agreeableness ($r = -0.437$, P value 0.01) and emotional stability ($r = -0.268$, P value 0.01) have significant negative correlation with burnout as indicated by significant r values. A regression analysis revealed that among the five personality traits, only conscientiousness ($\beta = -0.159$), agreeableness ($\beta = -0.34$) and emotional stability ($\beta = -0.132$) significantly determine burnout among the nurses.

Keywords: Agreeableness, Burnout, Nurses, Personality traits.

What is already known about the topic?

- Burnout resulting in poor performance at the workplace is common among the nursing professionals.
- Nurses are at a moderate to high risk of developing burnout, due to their hectic work schedule.
- Personality traits determine burnout significantly.

What this paper adds

- This paper presents a study of role of personality traits towards burnout among the nurses, by using a quantitative and correlational research design.
- It focuses on self-management and specific training programmes as a means to prevent burnout, rather than simple communication programmes.
- The study has generated empirical data which can be used not only by psychometricians but also the policy makers working for the betterment of healthcare professionals and institutions, so as to increase the effectiveness of these institutions.

1. Background

The importance of the role of health care professionals in delivering the services to the society has prompted the experts to discuss, debate, and examine the multitude of practices to make them more productive. Nurses form the largest component of the health care workforce and the possibility of strengthening them to become partners and leaders in improving the delivery of care and the health care system as a whole and preventing them from psychological problems has grabbed the attention of researchers since a long time. The role of the nurse includes having to deal with and adapt to a variety of situations and events including caring for people with long term illnesses and conditions, people at the end of life, health promotion, as well as fundamental care such as bathing, comforting and assisting patients and their relatives (Fealy, 2004). Nursing is increasingly wide in scope and includes an ample range of work behaviors and role responsibilities. However, nurse's work within a climate of uncertainty and disempowerment with high organizational demands which makes them highly disposed

to stress (Hart, 2005). This condition threatens both physical and emotional wellbeing of nurses, which in turn may contribute to disengagement or withdrawal of nurses from their organizations (Sabine & William, 2007). According to Schaufeli and Janczur (1994), nurses' tasks are demanding because they work with the suffering, grief and death of people. Although burnout can occur in any occupation, nursing is considered as being inherently stressful and an above-average risk group regarding work stress (Demerouti, Bakker, Nachreiner & Schaufeli, 2000). Similar to other helping professions, the prevalence of burnout in nursing is particularly high, because of the high emotional and physical demands of this work (Greenglass, Burke & Fiksenbaum, 2001; Leiter & Maslach, 1988). Nurses who reported higher levels of burnout also reported suffering from depression, anxiety, sleep disturbances and significant memory impairment (Peterson, Demerouti, Bergstrom, Samuelsson, Asberg & Nygren, 2008). High burnout levels in nursing have been associated with heavy workloads (Greenglass, et al., 2001), inadequate staffing levels (Vahey, Aiken, Sloane, Clarke & Vargas, 2004), absenteeism (Michie & Williams, 2003), and turnover (Fochsen, Sjogren, Josephson & Lagerstrom, 2005). Many studies have examined burnout in relation to increased mortality, failure to rescue, and patient dissatisfaction (Vahey, et al., 2004; Leiter, Harvie & Frizzell, 1998).

Studies have revealed that there are some personality characteristics in their role as personal antecedents of burnout. Research studies indicate that variables like self-efficacy, self-esteem, locus of control, emotional stability, extraversion, conscientiousness, positive affectivity, negative affectivity, optimism, proactive personality and hardworking impact highly on burnout (Bateman & Crant, 1993; Maslach, Schaufeli & Leiter, 2001; Maslach & Jackson, 1984). In other words, high disharmony between job nature and job holder's nature leads into burnout (Maslach & Leiter, 2005). Buhler and Land (2003); Langelan, Bakker, Doornen and Schaufeli (2006); Mosert and Rothmann (2006); Kim, Shin and Swanger, 2009; Alarcon, Eschleman and Bowling, 2009; Chung and Harding, 2009; Soliemanifar and Shaabani (2012); Alsaawi, et al. (2014); Takemura, et al. (2015); Ang, et al. (2016) depicted that there exists a relationship between personality traits and burnout. However to ensure novelty all these variables have been taken together and studied especially on nurse population.

2. Methods

2.1 Study Population

The participants of the present study comprised of 300 nurses taken from eleven different hospitals/nursing homes of Baramulla District of Jammu and Kashmir, with inclusion criteria stated below:

The participant:

- Should possess the basic qualification required for the nursing job as prescribed by the hospital/recruitment authorities
- Have at least two years of working experience
- Should be performing the nursing job in the hospital/nursing home
- Should have been selected/engaged by the authorities and not working on voluntary basis.

All those nurses who fulfill above criteria have been taken for the present study which comprises of 300 nurses.

2.2 Study Design

A quantitative and correlational research design was adopted and the settings included hospitals/nursing homes of J&K, India. All the Block Medical Officers of Government Hospitals in Baramulla district of J&K, and the administrators of the Nursing homes were contacted for permission to carry the present study in their respective hospitals. After taking permission from the hospital authorities, nurses were personally contacted to get their responses. The researcher provided all help to the participants to understand the item/s of the questionnaire and the purpose of the study was explained to each participant. The investigator assured the confidentiality of the responses sought and verbal consent was taken from each participant in advance.

2.3 Objectives

The study was carried out with the following objectives.

1. To assess personality traits and burnout among the Nurses.
2. To study the relationship of personality traits with burnout among the Nurses.

3. To identify significant determinants of burnout among the big five personality traits (openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and emotional stability).

2.4 Study hypotheses

On the basis of objectives, the following hypotheses were formulated:

3. Study Measures

On the basis of objectives framed, the following hypotheses have been formulated:

- H1:** Openness trait is significantly correlated with burnout among nurses.
H2: Conscientiousness trait is significantly correlated with burnout among nurses.
H3: Extraversion trait is significantly correlated with burnout among nurses.
H4: Agreeableness trait is significantly correlated with burnout among nurses.
H5: Emotional stability trait is significantly correlated with burnout among nurses. **H6:** Openness trait will emerge as significant determinant of burnout in nurses.
H7: Conscientiousness trait will emerge as significant determinant of burnout in nurses.
H8: Extraversion trait will emerge as significant determinant of burnout in nurses.
H9: Agreeableness trait will emerge as significant determinant of burnout in nurses.
H10: Emotional stability trait will emerge as significant determinant of burnout in nurses.

3.1. Instrumentation

For the assessment of personality traits, Five Dimensional Personality Inventory (FDPI) (self-report form) developed by Muzamil and Shawkat (2015) was used. It is a 20 item instrument having 4 items in each of the five dimensions namely openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and emotional stability with strongly with strongly disagree, disagree, somewhat agree, neutral, somewhat agree, agree with strongly disagree, disagree, somewhat agree, neutral, somewhat agree, agree and strongly agree options for each item. The alpha coefficient in the present study for personality traits is 0.74 (see table 1.1).

The Maslach Burnout Inventory-Human Services Survey (MBI-HSS) (Maslach & Jackson, 1986) was used to measure burnout in this study. The MBI-HSS consists of 22 items that are scored on a seven-point frequency scale, ranging from 0 (never) to 6 (every day). The three subscales of the MBI-HSS include emotional exhaustion (nine items), depersonalization (five items), and personal accomplishment (eight items). The alpha coefficient in the present study for overall burnout is 0.76 (see table 1.1).

Baseline characteristic Questionnaire was constructed to obtain information regarding gender, type of hospital/nursing homes in which they are working, work experience, salary, marital status, etc.

3.2. Statistical Analysis

The responses obtained from the participants were subjected to different statistical treatments. Using SPSS 20.0, the data was subjected to descriptive (frequencies, percentages, mean, standard deviation), and inferential analysis like correlation, regression and t-test to meet the objectives of the study and to test the hypotheses. The level of significance chosen was 0.05.

4. Results and Interpretation

The results and their interpretation is reflected in the tables that follow.

Table 4.1: Scale Characteristics and Reliability Analysis of the Personality Trait Scale and Burnout Scale.

Measure	Items	Response Range	N	M	SD	Cronbach's alpha(α)
Personality Traits	15	1-7	300	85.48	9.06	.74
Burnout	20	0-6	300	40.77	16.35	.76

The above table reveals a satisfactory internal consistency of the measuring instruments as indicated by the alpha coefficient scores of 0.74 and 0.76 in case of personality traits and burnout respectively.

Table 4.2: Showing range of scores with indifferent levels of personality traits.

Personality traits	M	SD	LL-UL	Low	Average	High
Openness	5.99	.87	5.11-6.86	<5.11	5.11-6.86	>6.86
Conscientiousness	6.17	.65	5.52-6.83	<5.52	5.52-6.83	>6.83
Extraversion	5.97	.65	5.26-6.67	<5.26	5.26-6.67	>6.67
Agreeableness	5.96	.75	5.20-6.71	<5.20	5.20-6.71	>6.71
Emotional stability	4.38	1.67	2.70-6.06	<2.70	2.70-6.06	>6.06

LL=Lowerlimit; UL=Upperlimit

The above table reflects the mean and standardisation of the various personality traits. It also shows the lower and upper limits calculated in order to get the limits for grouping the individuals into low, average and high levels. In order to calculate lower limit, the standard deviation has been subtracted from the mean score and to get the upper limit standard deviation has been added to the mean score. Accordingly, any score upto the lower limit is considered low, any score from lower limit to upper limit is considered average and any score above the upper limit is considered high.

Table4.3: Showing frequency distribution of personality traits of Nurses.

Personality traits	Levels					
	Low		Average		High	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
Openness	35	11.67	217	72.33	48	16
Conscientiousness	44	14.67	188	62.67	68	22.66
Extraversion	36	12	190	63.34	74	24.66
Agreeableness	54	18	203	67.67	73	14.33
Emotionalstability	59	19.66	196	65.34	45	15

The above table indicates that 11.67% of nurses have low level of openness trait, 72.33% have average level and 16% of nurses are having high level of openness trait;14.67% of nurses have low level of conscientiousness trait, 62.67% have average level and 22.66% of nurses are having high level of conscientiousness trait;12% of nurses have low level of extraversion trait, 63.34% have average level and 24.66% of nurses are having high level of extraversion trait;18% of nurse's have low level of agreeableness trait, 67.67 % have average level and 14.33% of nurse's are having high level of agreeableness trait and .66% of nurse's have low level of emotional stability, 65.34% of nurse's have average level of emotional stability, and 15% of nurse's are having high level of emotional stability.

Table 4.4: Showing range of scores within different levels of burnout and its dimensions.

Variables	M	SD	LL-UL	Low	Average	High
Emotional exhaustion	2.98	1.42	1.56-4.41	<1.56	1.56-4.41	>4.41
Depersonalization	2.26	1.33	0.93-3.59	<0.93	0.93-3.59	>3.59
Lack of personal accomplishment	.88	.819	0.06-1.70	<0.06	0.06-1.70	>1.70
Burnout	2.04	.85	1.186-2.90	<1.186	1.186-2.904	>2.90

LL=Lowerlimit; UL=Upperlimit

The above table reflects the mean and standardisation of burnout and its dimensions. It also shows the lower and upper limits calculated in order to get the limits for grouping the individuals into low, average and high levels as per the same methodology as presented below the table 1.2.

Table4.5:Showing frequency distribution of nurses on burnout and its dimensions of burnout.

Variables	Levels					
	Low		Average		High	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
Emotionalexhaustion	62	20.67	170	56.66	68	22.67
Depersonalization	42	14	197	65.67	61	20.33
Lack of personal	42	14	214	71.34	44	14.66
Burnout	54	18	191	63.66	55	18.33

The table indicates that 18% of nurses were found to have low level of burnout, 63.66

have average level and 18.33 of nurses have high level of burnout;20.67% of nurses were found to have low level of emotional exhaustion

56.66% have average level and 22.67 % of nurses have high level of emotional exhaustion;14% of nurses have low level of depersonalization, 65.66% have average level and 20.33% of nurses have high level of depersonalization and 14% of nurses have low level of lack of personal accomplishment, 71.34% have average level and 14.66% of nurses have high level of lack of personal accomplishment.

Table 4.6: Showing Correlations of Personality traits with Burnout and its dimensions

Personality traits	Dimensions of Burnout			
	Burnout	Exhaustion	Depersonalization	Accomplishment
Openness	-.126*	.001	-.037	-.338**
Conscientiousness	-.317**	-.211**	-.227**	-.260**
Extraversion	-.246**	-.139*	-.117*	-.343**
Agreeableness	-.437**	-.420**	-.354**	-.068
Emotional stability	-.268**	-.284**	-.219**	.007

**Correlation is significant at 0.01 level. *Correlation is significant at 0.05 level.

The above table reflects that all the five personality traits: openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and emotional stability are significantly correlated with burnout. Therefore hypotheses H₁ to H₅ stand accepted. However, as far as the dimensions of burnout are concerned the correlation of openness trait with two dimensions of burnout viz; emotional exhaustion and depersonalization is insignificant, besides agreeableness and emotional stability trait also showed insignificant correlation with lack of personal accomplishment dimension of burnout.

Table 4.7(a): Showing Multiple Regression Analysis of Personality traits and burnout.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	53.786	5	10.757	18.930	.000
Residual	167.067	294	.568		
Total	220.853	299			

Table 4.7(b): Multiple Regression Analysis (Summary of Predictor Variables)

Predictors	B	SE B	β	t	Sig
Constant	6.073	.495		12.278	.000
Openness	-.064	.059	-.065	-1.093	.275
Conscientiousness	-.209	.084	-.159	-2.487	.013
Extraversion	-.088	.074	-.072	-1.175	.241
Agreeableness	-.386	.064	-.340	-6.020	.000
Emotional stability	-.068	.028	-.132	-2.454	.015

$R^2 = .244 (p < .005)$

The table shows that about 24.4% of variation in burnout of nurses can be attributed to their personality traits as the obtained $R^2 = .244 (p < .005)$. Further, among the five personality traits- conscientiousness, agreeableness and emotional stability were found significant predictors/determinants of burnout of nurses as their respective values ($\beta = -.159, p = .013; \beta = -$

.340, $p = .000$; $\beta = -.132$, $p = .015$) are significant at 0.05 level of significance. The negative sign of values indicate that strengthening of these personality traits will reduce burnout of nurses. Therefore hypothesis H7, H9, and H10 stand accepted whereas hypothesis H6 and H8 stands rejected.

5. Discussion & Conclusion

This study investigated how personality traits (openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and emotional stability) are related with burnout. As far as the descriptive analysis is concerned, in case of personality traits, the findings of the study are in line with the research carried out by Ang, *etal.* (2016) who found that most nurses fall low or average in neuroticism (high or average on emotional stability) and average or high in extraversion, openness, agreeableness, and conscientiousness dimensions of personality. Likewise, in case burnout, the results are in line with Alsaawi, *etal.* (2014) who found that the nurses are at a moderate to high risk of developing burnout.

The results of the correlational analyses as per which all the personality traits have significant negative correlation with burnout, are in line with the research carried out by Deary, Watson and Hogston (2003); Soliemanifar and Shaabani (2012); Dargah and Estalkhbijari (2012); Azeem (2013); and Magnano, Paolillo and Barrano (2015). The results of regression analysis as per which the conscientiousness, agreeableness and emotional stability significantly determine burnout among the Nurses, are also supported by many research evidences. Bakker, Van Der Zee, Lewing and Dollard (2006); Storm and Rothmann (2003); Zellars, Hochwarter, Perrewe, Hoffman and Ford (2004); Chung and Harding (2009); Takemura, *etal.* (2015); Alarcon, Eschleman and Bowling (2009) have highly stressed the role of personality traits in influencing the experience of burnout. Thus the present study has succeeded in modelling the relationship of personality traits with burnout and has yielded data which can be used not only by psychometricians but also the policy makers working for the betterment of healthcare professionals and institutions, so as to increase the effectiveness of these institutions.

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